

Citizens' rights and British Withdrawal Agreement beneficiaries in the EU, EEA and EFTA

Five years on from Brexit

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Executive summary

This report presents findings from the 2025 survey *Citizens' Rights and British Citizens in the EU, EEA and EFTA, five years on from Brexit*. Drawing on 1,599 valid responses, it offers an assessment of the ongoing implementation and application of the Withdrawal Agreement (WA)—and equivalent agreements with the EEA, EFTA states and Switzerland—in respect to the status and rights of British WA beneficiaries.

The report identifies that some of the initial issues with implementation have been resolved. It also reveals high rates of permanent residence among British WA beneficiaries living across the EU, EEA and EFTA, highlighting that the transition from temporary residence status to permanent status has been seamless in most member states.

However, the report also highlights several persistent issues faced by WA beneficiaries. These include:

- **Delays and administrative errors** in issuing residence documentation, particularly in countries with decentralised administrative systems
- **Inconsistent recognition of WA status** at borders and within the Schengen area, leading to passport stamping and denial of rights to entry and exit
- **Barriers to accessing healthcare, pensions, and social security**, especially for dependants and S1 holders
- **Discrimination and lack of equal treatment**, including cases involving disability and national origin

The survey reveals challenges that have developed as a consequence of evolving administrative and legal frameworks related to Brexit:

- **Barriers to accessing rights in everyday life**
In declaratory countries, the lack of mandatory residence documentation has often led to *de facto* requirements by local authorities and private intermediaries (e.g. banks, healthcare providers), creating obstacles to accessing services and rights.
- **Challenges for dual nationals and those with multiple statuses**
Respondents reported difficulties obtaining documentation that reflects their WA status alongside other legal statuses, despite EU guidance requiring member states to accommodate this.
- **Discrimination and lack of accessibility for disabled individuals**
The survey highlights a small number of cases where disabled WA beneficiaries were refused WA beneficiary status, instead encouraged to apply as dependants, or had faced inappropriate treatment during administrative procedures due to inflexible systems not designed with accessibility in mind.
- **Potential breaches of WA provisions**
The survey identified the limited provision for minors needing documentation of their WA beneficiary status, with minors in France covered by their parents' WA status denied residence cards when needed for employment or other activities.

These findings underscore the need for continued monitoring, targeted interventions, and improved administrative practices to ensure that British citizens living in the EU, EEA and EFTA can fully exercise their rights enshrined in the WA.

Introduction

This report investigates the lived experiences of British nationals who are beneficiaries of the Withdrawal Agreement (WA) living in the EU—and equivalent agreements with the EEA, EFTA states and Switzerland—focusing on the implementation and application of the citizens' rights provisions of the WA.¹ Drawing on 1,599 valid responses to a survey conducted in 2025, it provides a timely assessment of the extent to which the rights enshrined in the WA have been upheld across member states and identifies outstanding issues.

The survey was designed to capture a wide range of experiences, from securing residence status and documentation to accessing healthcare, employment, and social security. Through a combination of closed and open questions, it collected statistical data and qualitative insights that offer insights into the personal impacts of administrative practices, legal interpretations, and local implementation.

In particular, the report draws in these findings to highlight the progress that has been made since the initial implementation of the citizens' rights provisions, demonstrating how some historical challenges have been resolved, while drawing attention to longstanding, ongoing and new issues that have emerged—notably in relation to recognition of status, access to rights, and equal treatment. In this way, the report offers a grounded perspective on the evolving realities of post-Brexit life for British WA beneficiaries in the EU, EEA and EFTA.

Understanding the evidence

This report draws on data from the online survey 'Citizens' rights and British citizens in the EU, EEA and EFTA, five years on from Brexit', based on a non-probability sample of adult British WA beneficiaries and their family members living in the EU, EEA and EFTA.² The research was conducted independently by Professor Benson and her team, who are committed to maintaining the highest standards of impartiality and objectivity throughout the study, and funded by UK Government.

Data collection

Developing the survey questions took place in several stages. In the first instance, Professor Benson reviewed publicly available information on the continuing implementation of the WA for British citizens in the EU, EEA and EFTA. She supplemented this with exploratory conversations with members of civil society organisations. This scoping work helped to identify areas that could be explored in further depth through the questions.

The questions included in the survey were modelled on existing surveys including the Independent Monitoring Authority's 'Life in the UK after Brexit'³ and the Migration Observatory's 'Lived Experiences of the UK immigration system',⁴ to enable future comparability, albeit adjusted to allow for the different context. Questions about demographic data were modelled on UK census questions and the Office for National Statistics recommendations for survey

¹ Throughout the report, where we refer to the Withdrawal Agreement (WA) this should be understood as extending also to the other agreements.

² Non-probability sampling is a selection of individuals from a population where every member does not have an equal chance of being included. As such, the sampling method adopted non-random criteria, and is best understood as a convenience sample, where people who met the defined characteristics – being British, living in the EU, EEA, EFTA since before Brexit, could self-select to participate. As the population of British citizens living in the EU, EEA, and EFTA is not well-defined – for example, even statistical knowledge about this population is limited (Benson, M. 2019. The puzzle of how many Brits Abroad there really are, *BBC News Website*, 12 January 2019 [<https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-46632854>]), this was the most appropriate sampling methods.

³ See https://ima-citizensrights.org.uk/news_events/ima-launches-survey-for-eu-citizens-on-life-in-the-uk-after-brexit/

⁴ See <https://migrationobservatory.ox.ac.uk/resources/reports/migrants-experiences-of-the-uk-immigration-system/>

questions.⁵ The survey was trialled with representatives of civil society organisations, who offered feedback before the launch of the survey in June 2025.

Survey respondents were recruited via Facebook, X, LinkedIn, Bluesky and Instagram posts; mail outs from Consulates and Embassies; newspaper articles in local English-language newspapers (e.g. *The Local*; *The Connexion*); through the mailing lists for civil society organisations; and to former participants in research on this topic conducted by Professor Benson who had consented to being contacted about future research. There was one wave of data collection taking place in June and July 2025.

Respondents were asked about their residence status in their host State; their experiences of applying for this status and documentation proving that status; experiences of proving their legal status; their understandings of their post-Brexit rights as beneficiaries of the WA; accessing their rights and experiences of discrimination. We additionally collected demographic data. The majority of the questions were multiple-choice, with optional follow up open text opportunities for respondents to supply more detail.

After removing duplicates and ineligible responses (for example, where people had not filled in any or only a small number of responses), we excluded 336 responses from the survey. In total, there were **1,599 valid responses** which have been included in the analysis presented in this report.

Once the main survey was closed and initial analysis commenced, we discovered that the response to questions asking people to state their legal status in their country of residence had only been answered by 3% of those taking part. This was significantly lower than other core questions where the over 85% of people had responded. To improve the level of responses to this question, we followed up with those who had agreed to be contacted about the survey and follow up research (n=1358) and who had not completed the response and requested that they consider filling in these responses. This solicited a further 728 valid responses for this question, which we then incorporated into the original survey data.

Data analysis

Various breakdowns of the results are presented in each section of the report. These combine basic statistical analysis of multiple-choice questions alongside thematic analysis of the qualitative responses. Unless otherwise stated, our statistical analysis is of the full sample. We present only the data that directly addresses the aim of the report insights into the outstanding issues relating to the implementation and application of the WA.

Context

At the end of 2025, it will be five years since the end of the Brexit transition period. The vast majority of the estimated 1.2 million British citizens who were resident in the EU, EEA and EFTA before the end of transition period have now secured their status as WA beneficiaries and, where this is a requirement by their country of residence, been issued with residence cards.⁶

The implementation of the WA for British citizens living in the EU, EEA and EFTA was delegated to national authorities, with each country choosing whether to adopt a **constitutive approach** (n=17), requiring that people actively apply for a new status as WA beneficiaries, or a

⁵ See for example ONS guidance on collecting data on ethnic group, religion and national identity

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/classificationsandstandards/measuringequality/ethnicgroupnationalidentityandreligion>

⁶ Current statistics drawn from the United Nations Global Migration Database estimate that there were 1.54 million people born in Britain living in the EU countries in 2024; see Sturge, G. and Bolton, P. (2025) Migration Statistics, House of Commons Library Briefing SN0677, <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/SN06077/SN06077.pdf>

declaratory approach (n=14), which automatically conferred this new status on eligible individuals.

Early research had warned of the challenges that national and local governments might face in implementing the citizens' rights provisions.⁷ In the case of those countries operating constitutive systems, issues emerged as their application systems were rolled out and implemented. These included delays in launching systems; mistakes in processing applications and making decisions; delays in decision-making; and lack of communication to resident British citizens with consequences for individual lives. In declaratory countries, other issues emerged; these related mostly to the processes involved in securing documentation attesting to residence as WA beneficiaries.

For the large part, the historical issues relating to the initial implementation of the citizens' rights provisions have been resolved. Yet, as this report highlights, some issues remain, and with the passage of time, new issues have emerged particularly in respect to the recognition of rights.

Key survey demographics

Where were respondents living?

Table 1 breaks down responses by country for those states operating constitutive and declaratory systems for implementing citizens' rights respectively. The remaining respondents were not living in an EU, EEA, or EFTA member state at the end of the Brexit transition period but indicated exceptional circumstances that made them eligible for citizens' rights provisions.

Country	Total number of responses	Percentage of overall responses	Estimated size of British population (2019)
Austria	44	3%	13,000
Belgium	35	2%	23,231
Bulgaria	11	>1%	9,992
Croatia	1	>1%	618
Cyprus	18	1%	37,684
Czech Republic	27	2%	5,327
Denmark	47	3%	21,837
Estonia	3	>1%	789
Finland	23	1%	7,948
France	533	33%	176,672
Germany	62	4%	98,553
Greece	91	6%	17,230
Hungary	35	>1%	11,111
Iceland	2	>1%	

⁷ Benton, M., Ahad, A., Benson, M., Collins, K., McCarthy, H., and O'Reilly, K. (2018) *Next Steps: implementing a Brexit deal for UK citizens living in the EU-27*, Brussels: MPI Europe. Available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/research/implementing-brexit-deal-uk-citizens-eu>

Ireland	8	>1%	293,061
Italy	211	13%	65,645
Latvia	0	0%	2,985
Liechtenstein	0	0%	
Lithuania	2	>1%	4,568
Luxembourg	5	>1%	5,852
Malta	12	>1%	23,213
Norway	6	>1%	
Poland	35	2%	36,585
Portugal	61	4%	18,695
Romania	5	>1%	16,828
Slovakia	1	>1%	7,267
Slovenia	3	>1%	604
Spain	194	12%	302,020
Sweden	51	3%%	30,265
Switzerland	5	>1%	
The Netherlands	53	3%	55,445
Total	1584		

Table 1: Number and percentage of responses from British citizens living in EU, EEA and EFTA countries

Of the respondents to the survey, over half (58%) were living in one of three countries at the end of the Brexit transition period: France (33%); Italy (13%) and Spain (12%). The most recent estimated number of British citizens living in the EU list these countries in the within the top 5 destinations for British citizens living in the EU (alongside Ireland and Germany).⁸ As such, high number of responses from these countries reflects these broader patterns of British residence. The low number of responses from Ireland is common to other research about British citizens in the EU, EEA, or EFTA, likely because Brexit has had a lesser impact on daily life than in the case of other member states due to the Common Travel Area, a longstanding free movement regime between the UK and Ireland. We did, however, expect more responses from Germany given the large number of British citizens estimated to live there.

Within the remainder of the sample, there was at least one respondent from each EU, EEA or EFTA member state (with the exception of Latvia and Liechtenstein where there were no responses). 96% of survey respondents were living in the same country as at the end of the Brexit transition period; of the 4% who had moved on, 16 had moved back to the UK, 11 onward to France, and the remaining to a variety of destinations within and outside the EU, EEA and EFTA.

About the respondents

We highlight here some key statistics about the respondents to offer some further context to the survey responses.

⁸ Statistica (2019) Estimated number of British citizens living in the European Union in 2019, by member state, *Statistica* [website]. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1059795/uk-expats-in-europe/>

- 49% male, 51% female, in line with the UK's 2021 census data
- 96% identified as ethnically white; 4% as other than white, in contrast to the UK's 2021 census data where 81.7% of the population identified as white⁹
- 70% had degree-level or above qualifications in contrast to the UK's 2021 census data where 33.8% of the population responded that they had qualifications at this level
- 42% of respondents were over 65, therefore approaching or beyond retirement age
- among working age populations, the highest percentage of respondents (14%) were in the age group 60-64, with those aged 50-59 also relatively well-represented. The number of responses significantly decreased among younger, working age population, with only 1% aged 25-29, and no responses from those aged 18-24¹⁰
- 86% of respondents had been living in their current country of residence for more than 5 years, whilst 14% had done so for 2-5 years, 1% for 1-2 years and 1% for less than a year
- Participants' reasons for initially moving to their country of residence were work (21%); retirement (19%) and a partner or spouse (16%), followed by other (14%); family (6%); study (2%).

Legal Status

Unless otherwise stated, in this section, we draw mostly on responses solicited via our follow-up request. As such, the sample size for the responses about legal status reported below is **764**.

Across this sample, 18% had temporary residence, 57% had permanent residence, while the remainder held other statuses (e.g. dual EU-UK citizenship). There was a slight difference in the weighting of these statuses depending on whether countries had operated constitutive systems, where 58% of respondents reported that they held permanent residence, or declaratory systems, where 63% reported that they held permanent residence.

The seemingly high percentage of those reporting permanent residence is likely the consequence of the research taking place nearly five years since the end of the Brexit transition period, where we would expect that people have transitioned from temporary residence (limited to 5 years) to permanent residence. The marginally lower percentage of those in constitutive systems reporting that they hold permanent residence likely reflects delays in processes for acquiring documentation attesting to the transition from temporary to permanent residence, paired with the fact that many of those taking part in the survey conflated their status with the documentation attesting to this.¹¹

⁹ As previous research has demonstrated, research focused on British citizens and communities living overseas struggles to recruit ethnic minority Britons, despite knowledge and understanding that this population includes such individuals. See for example Benson, M. and Lewis, C. (2019) 'Brexit, British People of Colour in the EU-27 and everyday racism in Britain and Europe', *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 42(13): 2211-2228. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2019.1599134>.

¹⁰ More generally, research on Brexit has struggled to recruit younger British workers living in the EU, EEA and EFTA. Yet anecdotally there is evidence that these are among some of those who have faced the greatest challenges with securing their post-Brexit status and accessing their post-Brexit rights.

¹¹ At the time of writing, France had just announced that they had simplified the process of renewing WA Residence Permit Cards by allowing people to apply for these via an online portal (when previously they had had to apply through their local *préfecture* in person).

Key findings

In what follows, we reflect on some of the key findings from the survey. We combine statistical data to illustrate these, alongside qualitative responses that offer some further insights into the particular issues that people have and are facing.

Acquiring documentation

In this section, we consider ongoing issues faced by British citizens in the EU, EEA and EFTA in acquiring documentation attesting to their status as WA beneficiaries. The issues mentioned below correspond to Article 18 and specifically:

Article 18.1 (relating to constitutive systems):

The host state may require Union citizens or United Kingdom nationals, their respective family members and other persons, who reside in its territory in accordance with the conditions set out in this Title, to apply for a new residence status which confers the rights under this Title and a document evidencing such status which may be in digital form.

And Article 18.4 (relating to declaratory systems):

Where a host state has chosen not to require Union citizens or United Kingdom nationals, their family members, and other persons, residing in its territory in accordance with the conditions set out in this Title, to apply for the new residence status referred to in paragraph 1 as a condition for legal residence, those eligible for residence rights under this Title shall have the right to receive, in accordance with the conditions set out in Directive 2004/38/EC, a residence document, which may be in digital form, that includes a statement that it has been issued in accordance with this Agreement.

As 18.4 makes clear, new residence documents are not a requirement for lawful residence in host countries operating declaratory systems, yet many survey respondents living in declaratory countries identified that they had applied for such a residence document.

Applications for residence documents

When we asked people to rate their experience of applying for residence documents, the majority of respondents (75%) reported that applying for residence documents was extremely easy, somewhat easy, or neither easy nor difficult. The remaining 25% identified that this process has been somewhat difficult (20.5%) or extremely difficult (4.5%).

Figure 1: How would you describe your experience of applying for a residence document or card? A comparison of responses by those living in declaratory and constitutive systems

As Figure 1 demonstrates, those living in declaratory systems were slightly more likely to report that that applying for residence documents had been extremely or somewhat difficult.

In some countries, significant proportions of those responding to the survey reported the ease of applying. This was particularly notable for example in the case of the Netherlands (43% extremely easy) and Austria (36% extremely easy). Responses to the open text question asking respondents to add further detail often

highlighted the efficiency, clear organisation and communication of government and local authorities in these two countries, offering clear examples of how member states could facilitate access in line with the requirements laid out in the WA. For example, Austria had set up a dedicated Brexit hotline and opened dedicated offices to deal with this.

At the other end of the scale, survey respondents in Italy, Portugal and Germany—all countries operating declaratory systems—disproportionately responded that the process of applying for documentation had been somewhat or extremely difficult. Respectively, 39% of respondents in Italy, 33% in Portugal and 29% in Germany reported that this was the case.

It is notable that in countries where the administration relating to WA beneficiaries' residence was incorporated into existing systems for processing immigration status, individuals had faced more challenges in applying for their status or for documentation.

Even when survey respondents had found it relatively easy to apply for residence documents, they reported challenges in applying. Most commonly reported among all responses were:

- gathering the right documents (28%)
- long waiting times for appointments or decisions (26%)
- lack of clear information or guidance (17%)
- understanding the requirements (15%)
- language barriers (14%)

This set of issues was raised by the UK at the Specialised Committee for Citizens' Rights in June 2024, where they highlighted challenges faced by British WA beneficiaries in evidencing permanent residence rights; the lack of provision of appointments to acquire residence cards in some member states; and called for greater guidance and clarity on the evidence needed to apply for this documentation.¹²

Long waiting times for appointments

One of the most common issues that people reported in respect to their applications for documentation related to securing appointments to initiate or complete this process. When asked about challenges faced in applying for documentation, long waiting times for appointments and decisions was an issue selected by the highest proportions of participants in Portugal (41%); Italy (35%) and Spain (33%), as contrasted, for example, to 26% of participants in France. In Italy alone, there were at least 20 separate reports about the lack of response to requests for appointments.

It took me almost two years to complete the process. The longest delay was obtaining an appointment at the Questura [local headquarters for the state police] and then after submitting my application, obtaining an appointment to go and collect my card.¹³ (Italy)

I was entitled to a permanent residency at the time of applying for my Withdrawal Agreement biometric card, but I was sent a 5-year temporary card. I have been trying, unsuccessfully, since to make an appointment with the immigration department to apply for permanent residency but have been refused as they are so far behind. (Portugal)

Not enough appointment slots resulting in difficulty getting an appointment in the correct time frame. (Spain)

Such cases signal an ongoing issue with appointment availability, and in cases where such documentation may be necessary to access rights as per the WA, can be understood as a barrier to accessibility, in contravention of the legal duties of EU member states to facilitate this access.

Additionally, in Spain, 15 respondents signalled that it was impossible for them to get appointments without hiring a *gestor*, an intermediary helping them to navigate this complex and bureaucratic process.

¹² See <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/citizens-rights-specialised-committee-meeting-6-june-2024-joint-statement>

¹³ In Italy, the Questura [local headquarters for the state police] are responsible for administration in respect to immigration, including the processing of documentation relating to residence.

Without the help of a gestor to get the appointments or the invaluable help of a relocation agent, we would not have been able to get our residency sorted. It's too complicated, no appointments, documents required changes with each appointment and without warning (Spain)

This signals that the process of applying for documentation is overly complicated. For those who cannot afford to hire someone to support them through this process, this could potentially have implications for their access to their rights under the WA.

Local Government Officials and the lawful application of the WA

A common issue encountered were discrepancies between publicly available information on application requirements versus what was demanded at appointments or in encounters with state officials. There are at least 23 separate mentions of this across several of the open text questions in the survey; with the highest numbers of responses about France (9) and Italy (7).

This contravenes the relevant provision in Directive 2004/38/EC (Recital 14), which was used as the basis for the issuance of residence documents within the WA:

The supporting documents required by the competent authorities for the issuing of a registration certificate or of a residence card should be comprehensively specified in order to avoid divergent administrative practices or interpretations constituting an undue obstacle to the exercise of the right of residence by Union citizens and their family members.

As such, responses indicating that competent authorities were adopting different practices and expectations suggest issues in the lawful application of the WA.

Each official we saw suggested other documents that were required. No one seemed to have a clue what the left or right hand was doing. (Greece)

A list of required documents was given, but at the appointment more was asked for. (France)

Personnel at the office of immigration requested additional documents. It seemed that the local authorities here made their own decisions, paying little attention to the formal guidelines. (Italy)

This challenge seemed to be particularly acute in countries where the process of issuing documentation was decentralised, delegated to local or municipal civil servants. Respondents highlighted their concerns that local civil servants had not received training or communications about citizens' rights and the WA, while recognising that this was only a small part of their wider portfolio:

Being such a small cohort with a 'special' status, and with things managed in such a decentralised way, means that public officials often don't know about us and our rights. (Italy)

A relative lack of understanding (including an apparent lack of knowledge of the Interior Ministry's guidance document about this) on the part of the local Ausländerbehörde [the Foreigner's Office] dealing with the claim to a WA GB Aufenthaltstitel [residence permit], and the differences between these and other more general German residence rights and associated cards. (Germany)

Respondents in several countries provided concrete examples of how the lack of knowledge among local officials administering the implementation of the WA had resulted in challenges in securing documentation certifying their status as WA beneficiaries:

Local authority not knowing the rules of Art. 50 and attempting to deny me a residence card. (Malta)

This mismatch between publicly available information about the implementation of the WA and the knowledge and expectations of local bureaucrats tasked with administering the process has been repeatedly flagged by research with British citizens living in the EU.¹⁴ It persists despite

¹⁴ See for example Benson, M., Zambelli, E., Craven, C. and Sigona, N. (2022) *British Citizens in the EU after Brexit*. MIGZEN Research Brief, No. 1 [Online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6515640>; Benson, M. (2020) *Brexit and the British in France*. Project report: ES/R000875/1 BrExpats [Online] Available at: <https://research.gold.ac.uk/id/eprint/28222/>

member states highlighting that they have provided such training at local level as outlined in the reports from the Specialised Committee.¹⁵

Administrative errors and delays

There were a significant number of responses reporting that individuals in several countries had been issued residence cards and other documentation that incorrectly listed their residence status – most often as temporary rather than permanent – or issued these for a shorter time frame than the applicants had expected (5 rather than 10 years). Given that the rights pertaining to temporary and permanent residence differ, with the latter offering greater security to its holders, the consequences of being issued with the incorrect documentation are significant.

While in many of the cases reported to us through the survey there was not enough information provided by respondents to gauge whether individuals met the eligibility requirements (beyond having lived in the country for a period of time) laid out in Article 15(1), some respondents made clear that they had appealed with the support of external agencies:

The authorities granted my spouse a 5-year permit. I questioned this at a higher authority, and they then issued a 10-year one. (France)

The Questura¹⁶ gave me the wrong card which I refused. Refused to listen and were rude and dismissive. I had to complain to UNHCR [United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees]. (Italy)

Originally issued a 5-year card whereas I was entitled to a 10-year permanent card. Sorted through IOM [International Organisation for Migration]. (Italy)

For these respondents, exercising their right to appeal as laid out in Article 21 had resulted in positive outcomes. This makes clear that issues remain both in respect to administrative errors and delays, with potential consequences for individuals concerned.

Refusals of applications for documentation

France, minors and residence documents

In France, British minors living with parents or guardians covered by the WA cannot apply for a *Carte / Titre de Séjour – Accord de retrait du Royaume-Uni de l'EU* [France's WA residence permits]. This is in line with France's approach to foreign minors. British WA beneficiaries previously covered by their parent or guardian's status must apply for their own WA residence permit within a year of turning 18. Yet, as the following quotation illustrates there are certain conditions under which such a card may be necessary for those under the age of 18:

Our only challenge arose when our son turned 16 and was offered a summer job which required him to have a residence card in his own right. Minors come under their parents until they want to work. Prefecture led us round in circles until we eventually used RIFT [Grassroots organisation – Remain in France Together] to escalate it and quoted the law to the Prefecture.

There is no universal provision in France for those under the age of 18 to acquire such a document. As *FrenchEntrée* reports:

It is possible in some circumstances for children between the ages of 16 and 18 to apply for a carte de séjour, but this depends on the prefecture. Prefectures that do issues such cards only do so if there is a specific reason, such as undertaking a work permit that requires such a permit.¹⁷

¹⁵ The joint reports on residence issued by the Specialised Committee on Citizens' Rights listed the measures undertaken by individual member states in anticipation of such issues. These can be found at:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/specialised-committee-on-citizens-rights>

¹⁶ In Italy, the Questura [local headquarters for the state police] are responsible for administration in respect to immigration, including the processing of documentation relating to residence.

¹⁷ French Entrée (2024) Reader Q: Are my children covered by the Withdrawal Agreement when they turn 18? Available online at: <https://www.frenchentree.com/brexit/reader-q-are-my-children-covered-by-the-withdrawal-agreement-when-they-turn-18/>

In initially denying this individual a residence card, the prefecture jeopardized his right to work as conferred by his status as a WA beneficiary. Such cases where WA beneficiaries under the age of 18 are denied their own residence documents attesting to their status potentially breaches the provisions of the WA.

Refusal to issue documentation to those with multiple statuses

The personal scope of the WA extends to dual EU/UK nationals under the conditions laid out in Article 10. As the European Commission (EC) has made clear, UK nationals may hold multiple immigration statuses in their country of residence and choose which of these to rely on in any given context. The EC states:

This means that the host State must, where the relevant conditions are fulfilled, recognise that a Withdrawal Agreement beneficiary has multiple statuses. It also means that Withdrawal Agreement beneficiaries should be able to hold separate documents reflecting their individual immigration statuses.¹⁸

The responses to the survey reveal that securing documentation attesting to multiple immigration statuses continues to be an issue for many dual EU/UK nationals.

I am now (since 2021) a Dutch/British dual national, whilst retaining my WA beneficiary status. As one is required to hand in the Art 50 card on receiving Dutch passport/ID card, I currently have no way to prove my continuing WA status. (The Netherlands)

My wife had one issue; she was told that she did not need a Art. 50 card as we already had TdS [permanent residence permit]. After raising a complaint, the application was processed in 45 minutes. (France)

The European Commission has stated in its guidance notes that Withdrawal Agreement beneficiaries can hold multiple statuses including the EU long-term permit. My son went through a very lengthy and expensive process to get it only to find at his appointment at the immigration office that the national computer system would not accept a British application. We wasted a lot of time and money, and this had a considerable negative impact on him being able to complete his university studies in the Netherlands. He should have been entitled to fees for EU students not international fees. It delayed him being able to start his Master's. (Italy)

This is a longstanding issue that was first reported to the Specialised Committee on Citizens' Rights in November 2022.¹⁹ This refusal to issue separate documentation attesting to their status as WA beneficiaries to those with multiple statuses was reported by survey respondents in several member states including the Netherlands, Luxembourg and Italy. As the quotations above demonstrate, the issue seems to be that the systems that are used to process immigration status are not set up to accommodate multiple statuses. Yet, this contravenes the obligation placed by the EC on member states to issue separate documents to those with multiple statuses.

Rights and discrimination

In this section, we consider the knowledge and understanding among survey respondents of their rights as WA beneficiaries; their experiences of proving their status and exercising these rights; and any cases of discrimination.

¹⁸ European Commission (nd) *United Kingdom Nationals and Multiple Immigration Statuses*. Available Online at: https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/21a670b9-8f64-4de3-9912-ba5400e911f2_en?filename=united_kingdom_nationals_and_multiple_immigration_statuses_en.pdf

¹⁹ See <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/citizens-rights-specialised-committee-meeting-17-november-2022-joint-statement>

Awareness of rights

As Figure 2 demonstrates, when asked about the sources of information that had informed their knowledge and understanding of the changes to their status and rights, respondents were less likely to report that they had heard about these from official sources such as the EC, local authorities, embassies and consulates, than to report that they had heard about these from civil society organisations (38%) organisations specialising in citizens' rights (e.g. British in Europe; British in Italy) or from 'Other' (28%) sources—within this people identified that they had gained their knowledge from Facebook and other social media groups, notably from the pages of groups that were part of the *British in Europe* coalition (e.g. Brits in Greece; Brits in Austria).

Figure 2: From which organisations did you first hear about your status and rights under the WA or relevant Separation Agreements?

Significantly, responses regularly made clear that without these grassroots sources of information, they would have struggled to find the relevant information:

If I hadn't joined Facebook page 'Brits in Greece' I would not have had any idea what was happening. (Greece).

If it were not for 'Brits in Sweden' Facebook page, I doubt I could have navigated the process anywhere near as smoothly. Migrationsverket [Swedish Migration Agency] & Skatteverket [Swedish Tax Agency] have consistently given me the incorrect information when I have contacted them. (Sweden)

Other notable sources of information about their status, rights and the implementation process, were legacy news and media (e.g. BBC, Guardian), as well as English language newspapers (e.g. *Connexion*, *The Local*).

The majority of the survey respondents indicated that they were aware of their rights to live in and travel into and out of their country of residence (90%); rights to access healthcare services (80%), buy and rent property (80%) and right to work (80%). However, there was a lower level of awareness of other rights enshrined in the WA including, the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination (67%), the right to access state pensions (60%); the right to access social security benefits (56%), the right to study (49%), the right to family reunification under certain conditions (41%) and the right to access housing support (24%).²⁰

²⁰ The lower level of awareness of these rights is also echoed in the findings from the grassroots coalition British in Europe through their ICE Project Grassroots Survey. Available at: <http://bit.ly/4nEVXle>

Proving residence status and accessing rights

Recognition of (proof of) status and rights continues to be an issue for some British WA beneficiaries living in the EU, EEA, and EFTA. When asked if they had faced issues in proving or having their residence status recognised since Brexit, 13% of respondents reported having such issues. Of those who reported having such issues, nearly 50% (n=93) highlighted that they had faced these issues in the past 12 months, demonstrating the ongoing nature of this issue. This was unevenly spread across the different members states; with Italy the country with the largest proportion of responses reporting such issues at 24% (n=50). Across the survey, respondents who elaborated on the issues that they had faced in proving or having their residence status recognised, 45% (n=72) described the problem as one of not having their proof of status accepted by the person checking.

In many cases, the issues that respondents faced in proving their status were connected to the issues they faced in accessing their rights. When asked to identify whether they had had any difficulties in accessing their rights for themselves or family members, 23% (n=371) of all survey respondents reported such difficulties. As we discuss in further detail below, these difficulties in proving their status occurred in their interactions with employers, public officials (e.g. border guards, police officers, local bureaucrats) and healthcare providers. But it also framed encounters such as opening a bank account, buying and renting property, buying or leasing a car, or setting up a phone contract, where intermediaries insisted on forms of identification that WA beneficiaries were not entitled to, while not recognising their proof of residence.

At the borders

As Figure 3 demonstrates, the most reported issue survey respondents faced was having their residence documents recognised was by immigration officials.

Figure 3: In which of the following areas did you experience problems in proving or having your residence status recognised?

In turn, this created issues for their exercise of the right to exit, and entry as laid out in Article 14, and specifically:

2. No exit visa, entry visa or equivalent formality shall be required of holders of a valid document issued in accordance with Article 18 or 26.

Of survey respondents who identified that they had faced issues in having their residence documents recognised, 50% (n=189) identified that these issues had presented themselves at borders, in their interactions with immigration officials. As the further details that many of them

offered in their open text responses identified, a key issue seemed to be that their residence documentation and the rights this permitted were not recognised by immigration officials. The consequence was that their passports were unnecessarily stamped on entering or exiting their country of residence or when transiting through other countries within the Schengen area. In some cases, this led to them being questioned about why they were in the Schengen area for a period exceeding the 90 days permitted for visitors.

The rules for UK nationals when entering or leaving the Schengen area state:

The Commission recommends – notably as regards beneficiaries of the Withdrawal Agreement – that Member State border guards refrain from stamping. In any case, should stamping nevertheless take place, such stamp cannot affect the length of the authorised long-term stay.²¹

As the following examples make clear, the issues are not necessarily when they enter or exit their country of residence, but rather when they are transiting through other countries within the Schengen Zone:

I faced few difficulties entering or exiting the Netherlands, but I did face difficulties entering France after returning to the EU after travelling to Hong Kong, where the immigration official did not recognise my verblijfstitel [Dutch residency card under Art. 50] and stamped my passport as a UK tourist. This proved impossible to remove. I imagine the official did not recognise the permit because the information was in Dutch and I was entering the EU via a different country. (The Netherlands)

The German authorities recognise my residence status ... [H]owever, French border guards do not recognize my residence status, so that my passport has been stamped when crossing French-UK border.” (Germany)

In some cases, this has led to knock on impacts, as the following examples offered by respondents demonstrate:

We have not had problems in Norway, but we have had problems entering and leaving other EU countries. Our passports were stamped in error in the Netherlands and then we tried to enter Greece 6 months later and were threatened with a fine for overstaying our allowed time in the EU despite having proof of Norwegian residence. (Norway)

While evidence of status as a WA beneficiary issued by the host member state should be sufficient – whether a residence card or joining family member visa – for the purposes of exercising the right to entry and exit, the lack of literacy among border officials about the forms this takes, with the range of documents not necessarily in a common language, has resulted in the issues reported above.

With the introduction of the European Entry and Exit System (EES), any WA beneficiaries not in possession of an accepted residence document—a circumstance common among those who live in countries which adopted a declaratory approach to the implementation of the WA—are likely to face further issues in exercising their right to entry and exit of the Schengen area.²² This is because, while there is no requirement for WA beneficiaries to undergo EES registration, to be exempt they will be required to show a residence permit for their country of residence.

Employment

A total of 24% of survey respondents reported having their proof of status and related rights not recognised when (a) applying for employment (13%) and (b) in the workplace/from an employer (11%). The quotations below have been selected to demonstrate the impacts on their ability to exercise their rights as workers as laid out in Article 24.

²¹ European Commission (2024) Rules for UK nationals when entering or leaving the Schengen Area. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/adc8f329-17b3-4345-9e1b-ba509e6475dd_en?filename=2024%20guidance%20-%20Schengen.pdf

²² See https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/05752d5e-2e7f-4928-9678-d0addca29d88_en

I've been turned down for jobs because they assumed I needed a sponsorship to work here on a permanent visa. I've had phone calls from recruiters telling me I'm harder to employ because they wrongly assumed I needed sponsorship. (The Netherlands)

The companies didn't believe I had the same rights as a Hungarian citizen until they looked it up. I wonder how many companies didn't even bother checking before moving onto the next candidate. (Hungary)

Back in 2021, my future employer did not want to hire me as I did not have a permit of stay card, despite having my mandatory Withdrawal Agreement [residence permit]. The permit of stay card is not mandatory. I ended up not getting the job and applied for the card, even though it was not a legal requirement. (Italy)

These examples contravene Article 24(1)(b):

The right to take up and pursue an activity in accordance with the rules applicable to nationals of the host State or State of work.

As these quotations highlight, some employers and intermediaries such as recruitment agents are still unaware of the rights of WA beneficiaries, or the documentation they are or are not required to hold.

My then-employer decided incorrectly that holding an Article 50 card disqualified me (and dozens of others) from various employment benefits. We (myself and 16 colleagues) won that case at the employer's internal arbitration board [IAB]. (Austria)

This respondent from Austria further identified that the decision of the IAB had not been accepted by the management of their organisation, leading to further prolonged legal action and continued loss of employment benefits and income. As such, this example specifically identifies that in addition to the rights enshrined in Article 24(1)(b), British WA beneficiaries found that they were not able to exercise their right to social and tax advantages as laid out in Article 24(1)(e).

In everyday life

This lack of recognition of proof of status and related rights extends into people's encounters with other intermediaries, whether those employed by the state or otherwise. Those who did not hold a residence card attesting to their status as WA beneficiaries, notably those living in countries operating a declaratory system, faced particular challenges.

The following responses from individuals living in Italy—which adopted a declaratory system and where WA beneficiaries are not required to hold a residence card attesting to their status—illustrate a lack of recognition and understanding of WA rights by competent authorities such as the town hall or police, as well as other intermediaries.

Receiving a letter from my town hall demanding I present my Withdrawal Agreement card within 30 days or risk having my residency cancelled. I complied and they registered my card which they should not have done as the card is not mandatory in declaratory countries.

A policeman turning up at my house telling me I must register immediately (I had done so and had a permesso di soggiorno [non-EU national residency document]). He said if I didn't register, I faced deportation.

They wanted an EU Permesso di Soggiorno for the healthcare and also for INPS [social security and pensions]. It was difficult to get them to accept the CdS Brexit card [Carta di soggiorno per cittadini britannici ai sensi dell'Accordo di recess – Residence card for WA beneficiaries]. None of them would accept my permanent residence paper document. It was a stressful and exhausting procedure but now solved.

In Italy different documents are issued by the local commune and the provincial questura [local policy headquarters]. I had a problem with the local officials because they didn't really understand the law and took some persuasion to issue a document required in order to access local health services.

British WA beneficiaries in Italy are not required to hold a *permesso di soggiorno*, which is issued to non-EU residents. They may apply for a *carta di soggiorno elettronica* (biometric card) if they choose to, but this is also not obligatory. As such, local administrators and bureaucrats requesting such documents for individuals to exercise their rights to residence and other rights breaches the terms of the WA.

While the examples above demonstrate that this is a particular problem in Italy, this discrepancy also occurred in other jurisdictions and with non-state intermediaries.

For example, of those providing further details about the challenges they had faced (n=189), 16% (n=30) drew attention to the issues they had had in proving their status in their encounters with banking. They found themselves required to provide documents that they were not required to hold, while finding their documentation as WA beneficiaries not recognised, with the consequences described below.

I could not actually open a German bank account until I had a specific German residency card and number which could prove to the bank my residency status, even though under the Declaratory system the status existed without the need for a card to evidence it. (Germany)

My bank froze my current account for almost 2 weeks claiming I needed to give them a residence permit. (Italy)

In other cases, survey respondents reported being denied access to mortgages or other kinds of loans on the grounds that they could not demonstrate that they had permanent residency.

Banks being unaware that I obtained automatic permanent residency after five years and refusing to discuss mortgage, etc. (Germany)

The banks treat you as full 3rd party citizen and do not offer loans or make the process extremely difficult. I am a British citizen but born in Iran. The Hungarian authorities and banks refuse to recognise my British citizenship on its own merits and consider me always to be an Iranian. So 90% of the time I get rejected and have to jump through additional checks. (Hungary)

While the WA does not cover the actions and practices of non-state intermediaries, such examples illustrate the lack of alignment between requirements at state level and what is recognised and required at non-state level when going about the business of everyday life. Although there may be no official requirement (in declaratory states) for people to hold a residence document that attests to their status as a WA beneficiary, the (potential) repercussions of not supplying this when requested by competent authorities and third parties, suggest that, *de facto*, such documents are obligatory in order for people to conduct their everyday lives.

This section demonstrates the issues faced by survey respondents in having their status recognised, and the consequences of this for their ability to exercise their rights as WA beneficiaries. Such issues seem particularly acute at the borders; in employment – whether when trying to secure a role and in exercising their rights to equal treatment in the workplace; as well as in various dimensions of everyday life from their encounters with representatives of the states and non-state intermediaries such as banks.

Further difficulties in accessing rights

In this final section, we reflect on further difficulties faced by survey respondents in accessing their rights enshrined in the WA, with 23% (n=371) respondents identifying that they had faced such issues.

As Figure 4 demonstrates, they had experienced such difficulties in a range of areas, with the most commonly cited: (a) difficulties accessing their right to healthcare (41%; n=151); (b) right to equal treatment and non-discrimination (31%; n=116); and (c) right to travel in and out of their country of residence (21%; n=77).

Figure 4: Have you experienced any difficulties in accessing rights for you or for a family or household member in your country of residence since Brexit?

Right to access healthcare services

In respect to access to healthcare, British WA beneficiaries are entitled to access healthcare on equal terms as nationals in their country of residence. While issues were reported in most member states, these seemed most acute in Portugal, Italy and Greece. Of those living in Portugal who responded to the survey, 23% (n=14) identified this as an issue; of those in Italy, 22% (n=46); and of those in Greece, 12% (n=11).

Responses elaborating on the challenges in accessing their right to healthcare made clear that people had faced increased administrative burdens; had had to contest local healthcare officials' and other gatekeepers' understandings of their rights; and faced challenges in getting their dependants registered for healthcare. This led in some cases to people being denied access to publicly funded healthcare on the same basis as nationals of that country, going against the terms of the WA under Article 23—the right to equal treatment, and specially in respect to social security coordination (Article 30).

Have been informed that I can access state healthcare free on gaining permanent residence after 5 years of temporary residence, this is disputed by our local healthcare provider, so I am unclear as what rights I have prior to reaching UK pension age. (Spain)

Our local ASL [azienda sanitaria locale – Local Health Authority] refused 4 times to give us access to a doctor until we had help from the embassy. (Italy)

Portugal's health service computer system doesn't allow registration without a social security number, even though a social security number is not a legal requirement. It has been extremely difficult to

persuade the staff at the local health centre that I am entitled to healthcare under the state system. (Portugal)

The following cases highlight the lack of equal treatment in respect to healthcare faced by dependants of WA beneficiaries, who are eligible for social security coordination on the basis that they are family members also residing in the country of residence.

[They] won't accept my husband for dependents' healthcare despite me working and holding an AMKA [Social Insurance Number]. (Greece)

Access to healthcare was based on local health boards who independently set the financial contribution required. Our local ASL decided that my wife had to be assessed separately, despite her being my dependent, and then the maximum payment each of in excess of €3500 per annum (each) for a period of less than 1 year. This was far in excess of what we could afford so we're forced to find cheaper, private, medical insurance and hope that we did not become unwell. (Italy)

To offer some context on this second example, when registering a family member, the ASL might require evidence not only that they are dependants (e.g. a marriage certificate) but also proof of economic dependence.

In countries where access to healthcare is linked to social security registration, problems with registering for this and being issued with relevant identification numbers (e.g. *carte vitale* (France), AMKA (Greece)) – which, as per Articles 23 and 30, British WA beneficiaries qualify for, provided they meet the same terms for nationals in receipt of these – resulted in them not being able to access their rights.

We needed a SNS EHIC card [Portuguese national health card], but social security did not realise we were eligible. Denied until we explained we were here pre-Brexit, but this shouldn't matter. (Portugal)

I am still trying to secure an AMKA number [social security number]. So far have paid privately for any health-related appointments (plus pay for private health insurance which is a condition of residency). I only recently discovered I should qualify for AMKA in my own right under WA but have yet to manage this. (Greece)

There were also reported issues faced by S1 holders – generally UK pensioners – whose healthcare costs continue to be covered by the UK. From the challenges of registering for a system which ordinarily relies on registration via a social security number, to reports of healthcare services refusing to take on British WA beneficiaries with an S1 because of the administrative burdens of claiming back funds, a range of issues were highlighted in the open text responses.

Getting medical care with a pensioners S1 certificate is impossible as the GPs refuse to register the patients since they have to claim back the funds from the NHS and it's too much trouble for them so despite being eligible for free health care we still have to go private to get a doctor. (Bulgaria)

This final point, which was raised by several S1 holders in Bulgaria points to a lack of equal treatment in respect to access to healthcare, which falls under Article 23.

Property rights

In respect to buying and renting property, 11% (n=20) of survey respondents reported facing such challenges. This includes being charged a third country / foreign national fee to buy property, while others stressed that since Brexit, they had experienced restrictions on their right to purchase land. Both of these violate their right to purchase property on an equal basis to EU citizens:

Charged a 3rd [country] national fee when buying property. (Hungary)

For house purchase we have to pay 500 Euros for foreigner purchase certificate. It is hard to find affordable property in Vienna but from hearsay just outside Vienna some permits are being stalled or denied or hiring a lawyer to defend [the] right is required. (Austria)

Since Brexit we no longer have the right to buy property with land even a small garden in our personal name, we now have to set up a company to purchase land whereas pre-Brexit we could buy as individuals. (Bulgaria)

Such issues were reported at the Specialised Committee on Citizens' Rights in December 2023.²³ Yet it seems there are outstanding issues in this area.

Pensions and benefits

In addition to access to healthcare, pensions and benefits is another area of social security coordination (Article 30) and equal treatment (Article 23) where survey respondents reported that they had faced issues. While only small numbers of people reported these issues, they nevertheless indicate some cause for concern about the extent to which this aspect of the WA is being upheld by member states. As the following examples demonstrate, the issues people faced include accessing their state pensions (9%; n=34), with particular issues being faced by those who have lived and worked in Greece; social security (including unemployment and child benefits) (14%; n=53); and housing support (4%; n=14). Examples that respondents gave include the following, albeit with very little context.

Applied for pension 13 months ago. I [have] not heard anything. Greek people hear in 2 months. (Greece)

Apparently, I am less eligible for full state pension than a Danish citizen would be. (Denmark)

The right to parental allowance was not made clear to me and I was denied about 4 weeks of payments. (Sweden)

What these responses demonstrate is a sense of frustration that might indicate a lack of equal treatment when it comes to social security coordination and to access to benefits more generally as per their right to equal treatment.

Right to family reunification

Over 10% (n=41) of respondents highlighted that they had faced issues accessing their rights to family reunification. Outside of France, Italy and Spain (each of which had 3% of survey respondents from those countries reporting difficulties with accessing right to family reunification), the highest proportions (*with more than one person reporting*) were: Hungary (6%; n=2) and Greece (3%; n=3). While the numbers here are small, the issues that were raised by respondents often include being judged that their relationship was not durable despite preceding Brexit for the required term and on grounds that included lack of recognition of homosexual relationships by the country of residence; and lack of recognition of longstanding partnerships where marriage had not taken place.

Discrimination

While 65% (n=1,042) of participants responded that they had not felt discriminated against by a public body in their country of residence, over 30% of those taking part reported that they had experienced such discrimination. Where respondents had experienced discrimination, the most common basis was national origin, selected by 15% (n=201). Yet, there was limited qualitative evidence provided to validate or elaborate on these claims further.

²³ See <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/citizens-rights-specialised-committee-meeting-4-december-2023-joint-statement>

However, throughout the survey respondents provided evidence of discrimination on other grounds including race, sexual orientation and, most notably, disability. 11% (n=158) of participants considered themselves to have a disability, and others identified that they had family members who were disabled. For some, this presented challenges when it came to applying for status as WA beneficiaries as the following examples illustrate:

My son is high functioning autistic but despite him being able to look after himself they would not allow him to get his residency unless I agreed to be fully responsible for all his costs. (Bulgaria)

In this first instance, a man with disability who is in a position to support himself is deemed not to be able to be a WA beneficiary in his own right but instead to be a dependant of his elderly mother. This signals discrimination on the grounds of disability.

My mother who applied at the same time as me was paralysed in one hand due to a stroke, but the Danish requirement to fingerprint her was so inflexible that they forced her completely paralysed and rigidly closed hand open and flattened it onto a fingerprinting screen, causing immense pain. There were no other options allowed. (Denmark)

In this second case, it is clear that the process for obtaining residence cards was not accessible for those with disabilities.

As these final quotations demonstrate, there are issues relating to discrimination that require further attention.

Conclusion

Five years on from the end of the Brexit transition period, this report has highlighted the complex and evolving realities faced by British WA beneficiaries in the EU, EEA and EFTA. While many have successfully secured residence status and transitioned to permanent residence, the respondents to the survey reveal several outstanding and unresolved issues relating to implementation and recognition of their rights under the WA.

The findings confirm that administrative inconsistencies, lack of awareness among officials, and barriers to accessing documentation continue to affect individuals' ability to exercise their rights. New issues have emerged, particularly around border recognition, access to services in declaratory countries, and the treatment of dual nationals and disabled individuals. These challenges are compounded by limited official communication, placing undue reliance on civil society organisations and peer networks.

British WA beneficiaries have become experts in navigating their own legal status, often compensating for gaps in institutional support. Their experiences underscore the need for continued monitoring, improved administrative practices, and stronger enforcement of the WA's provisions. As the UK and EU look ahead, ensuring the full and fair implementation of citizens' rights must remain a priority—both to uphold legal commitments and to safeguard the everyday lives of those affected.

Key Recommendations

Legal and Policy Compliance

- Monitor and report breaches of WA provisions, including those affecting minors and dual EU/UK nationals
- Monitor member states' adherence to their obligation to issue separate and multiple documents in the case of WA beneficiaries with multiple statuses, and request that the EU remind member states these obligations in line with EC guidance
- Promote equal treatment in access to rights, and address discrepancies in access to healthcare, pensions, and social security, particularly for dependants and S1 holders

Administrative Improvements

- Work with the EU to urge member states (e.g. Italy, Portugal, Spain) to streamline their appointment systems and improve access to appointments for residence documentation, particularly as high volumes of individuals are expected to upgrade to permanent residence over the coming months
- Recommend harmonisation of local practices with national guidance to reduce administrative errors and delays
- Call for enhanced training for local and border officials to ensure consistent recognition of WA rights and documents, including in respect to the forthcoming implementation of the EES
- Advocate for clear guidance to Schengen border officials to prevent unnecessary passport stamping and misclassification

Communication and Support

- Encourage EU institutions to improve outreach and visibility of WA-related information and rights
- Recognise and fund grassroots organisations that provide essential support and information to WA beneficiaries

Monitoring and Oversight

- Advocate for continued independent oversight via regular audits and continued reporting on WA implementation in member states, with dedicated input from affected citizens
- Call for member states to collect and release data on discrimination, equal treatment in respect to access to rights, and administrative practices

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